

TYPES AND PERCENTAGES OF MICROBES IN SAMPLES FROM THE VAGINA AND CERVIX OF COWS WITH ENDOMETRITIS.

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Abstract. When samples taken from the uterine vagina and cervix of cows infected with endometritis in farms were examined for colonies of microbes grown in nutrient media of Petri dishes, staphylococcus 31-39%, streptococcus 21-27%, Escherichia coli 17-29%, blue pus bacillus 11-15% , it was noted that fungi make up 7-13%.

Keywords. In a purebred cow, endometritis, secretions, bacteria, microbial species, staphylococcus, streptococcus, Escherichia coli, fungi, and Escherichia coli.

Relevance of the topic. When researching obstetric-gynecological diseases in cows, purulent-catarrhal endometritis accounted for 86.1-94.7% on average, catarrhal endometritis for 1.9-4.8%, fibrinous endometritis for 2.7-5.8%, postpartum necrotic endometritis determined that it was 0.7-2.8% [4,10].

In the conclusions of some researchers, when non-specific postpartum endometritis was detected in cows, it was mentioned that the disease occurred in 57.5-61.3% of cases in the winter-spring season, and in 37.5-45.3% in the autumn-winter season [5].

Postpartum septicemia is reported mainly in carnivorous animals as a complication of pathological births, as a complication of miscarriages and endometritis in heifers and cows. The causative agents of postpartum sepsis can often be hemolyzing streptococci, in some cases staphylococci, Escherichia coli, pneumococci, etc. When injured areas are infected with dangerous tumor bacilli, anaerobic staphylococci and streptococci, the general infection takes place with a predominance of putrefactive processes. When Cl. chauvoei, Cl. septicum, Cl. hustolyticum and other anaerobic bacteria develop, the general infection takes the form of gas gangrene [3,8].

The mucous membrane of the uterus can often become inflamed due to direct contact with microorganisms (streptococci, staphylococci, Escherichia coli, etc.) or passing through the vagina. In addition, germs sometimes enter the uterus through blood vessels[1].

In animals infected with sexually transmitted diseases, the cervix and its branches secreted the same and the same amount of microflora. Staphylococcus (golden, white and yellow), purulent stratococcus, enteric and multipurulent bacillus, diplococci were distinguished in endometritis of cows. In most cases streptococcus and diplococci were isolated from the uterus of sick cows. 9 cows isolated streptococcus, diplococci and other cocci in their uterus, and in 20 cattle this condition ended with clinical recovery. [2; 6,7,9].

The purpose of the study. Taking into account the above, it is necessary to determine the factors that cause postpartum endometritis among foreign bred cows in our country, the types and percentages of microbes in the samples taken from the uterus and cervix of cows.

Research object and methods. Scientific investigation of the types, percentages and biochemical and plasmacoagulase properties of samples taken from the vagina and cervix of cows in postpartum endometritis at the "Farovon Grand Invest" livestock farm, Okdarya district, Samarkand region, as well as the Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology University It was conducted in the laboratory of the "Epizootology, microbiology and virology" department.

All large horned animals kept in the experimental livestock farms were examined for obstetric and gynecological diseases. For this, general and laboratory tests were conducted.

In the general examinations, the general condition of the animals was checked, the uterus was examined by manual palpation through the rectum, and attention was paid to the discharge of mucous substances from the cow's vagina.

In laboratory tests, samples were taken from the vagina and cervix of cows infected with endometritis according to the methods of N.N. Mikhaylov and others. Microbiological, that is, generally accepted bacteriological methods of testing were used in the examination of the samples.

In this case, samples taken from the uterus and cervix of cows with endometritis were cultured in different nutrient media. A pure culture was isolated from the microflora colonies developed in the nutrient medium. Cultivated nutrient media were placed in a thermostat (Heratherm 1MI 41839123).

Analysis of the obtained results: Biochemical and plasmocoagulase properties of samples taken from the vagina and cervix of five domestic cows with endometritis were studied in laboratory conditions using the invitron method.

Samples taken from the vagina and cervix of infected cows were planted in sterilized Petri dishes containing Streptococcus nutrient medium Velli agar,

Staphylococcus nutrient medium Shayli agar, Blue pus bacillus nutrient medium Difko agar using special sterile swabs. Culture media were placed in a thermostat (Heratherm 1MI 41839123) and examined after 24 hours at 37 C. Streptococcus colony was red in color, indicating malnitis produced acid by decomposition, Staphylococcus aureus was yellow, similar to lemon peel color, and Pseudomonas aeruginosa colony was cream in color. it looked

When the samples taken from the uterine vagina and neck of five head of domestic cows infected with endometritis were examined for colonies of microbes grown in nutrient media of Petri dishes, staphylococcus 31-39%, streptococcus 21-27%, Escherichia coli 17-29%, blue pus bacillus 11-15 %, fungi are found to be 7-13% (Table 1).

Types and percentages of microbes in vaginal and cervical samples in postpartum endometritis.

Table 1

Nº	Types of microbes	Nº 1214	Nº5031	Nº 07103	Nº 3799	Nº 3794
1	Staphylococcus	36%	35%	39%	33%	31%
2	Streptococcus	23%	21%	23%	27%	21%
3	Eshrixi colli	17%	19%	17%	21%	29%
4	Blue pus	13%	15%	11%	15%	11%
5	Zambrug's	11%	9%	9%	13%	7%
6	Total	100%	99%	99%	99%	99%

Summary

1. Samples taken from the uterine vagina and cervix of cows infected with endometritis at the "Farovon Grand Invest" cattle farm, Okdarya district, Samarkand region were examined for the colonies of microbes planted in Petri dishes.

2. Samples taken from the vagina and cervix of five domestic cows infected with endometritis, when examining the colonies of microbes grown in petri dish media, staphylococcus 31-39%, streptococcus 21-27%, Escherichia coli 17-29%, blue pus bacillus 11 It was noted that -15%, fungi make up 7-13%.

References:

1. Ата-Курбанов Ш.Б., Б.М.Эшбуриев. Ветеринария акушерлиги фанидан амалий – лаборатория машғулотлари. Самарқанд, 2009. 236.б
2. Алехин Ю. Н. Значение энергетического питания в обеспечении репродуктивной функции коров [Текст] / Ю. Н. Алехин // Современные проблемы ветеринарного обеспечения репродуктивного здоровья животных: Сб. науч. трудов. - Воронеж, 2009. - С. 28-32.
3. Баймишев Х.Б., Землянкин В.В., Баймишев М.Х. Практикум по ветакушерству и гинекологии. Самара, 2012.
4. Кузьмич Р.Г. и др. Лечебно-профилактические мероприятия при акушерских и гинекологических болезнях коров. Метод. Пособ. Витебск. 2012. 44 с.
5. Новикова Е. Н. Биопрофилактика эндометритов у коров [Текст] / Е. Н. Новикова, И. С. Коба, М. Б. Решетка // Животноводство Юга России. - 2015. - №5(7). - С. 32-34.
6. Епанчинцева О.С. Анализ эффективности методов профилактики послеродовых осложнений у коров / О.С. Епанчинцева // Мат. Междунар. науч.- практич. интернет-конф. «Современные тенденции в ветеринарной медицине» 21 ноября 2012 г. - Вестник ветеринарии, №63 (4/2012). – С. 77-79. 7.
7. Епанчинцева О.С. Микробный пейзаж содержимого матки и секрета молочной железы коров при послеродовой патологии // Мат. Междунар. науч.- практич. интернет-конф. «Современные тенденции в ветеринарной медицине» 21 ноября 2012 г. - Вестник ветеринарии, Краснодар № 63 (4/2012). – С. 42-44.
8. Эшбуриев Б.М., Эшбуриев С.Б., Жуманов С.М. Ветеринария акушерлиги фанидан амалий лаборатория машғулотлари. Ўқув қўлланма. СамДУ тахририй-нашриёт бўлими. ISBN: 978-9943-6319-7-7. Самарқанд. 2020. 319 б.
9. Хуранов А. М. Цитологическая дифференциальная диагностика состояния органов размножения у коров до- и после оплодотворения. Автореф. дисс.канд. вет наук. Москва – 2010.
10. Janowsli, T. Untersuchungen uber Progesterofile bei Kuhen mit puerperalen Endometritiden [Text] / T. Janowsli, S. Zdunczyk, A. Chmielewski, E. Mwaanda // Tierarzti. Umsch. - 2004. - №7. - S. 399-402.